

Human Existential Risk the Uses of Artificial Intelligence: A Philosophical Analysis

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Abstract: *The advance of artificial intelligence (AI) poses unprecedented challenges and opportunities for humanity. As AI continues to advance rapidly, the concept of existential risk emerges as a critical concern. This risk could threaten civilisation's survival or humanity's long-term path. This paper explores the key philosophical dimensions of existential risk associated with AI, addressing questions about moral responsibility, autonomy, identity, value position, and the implications for future generations. By drawing on ethical theories and existing literature, this analysis sheds light on the nuanced relationship between AI development and existential risk, emphasising the urgency for a responsible approach to AI ethics.*

Keywords: *Artificial intelligence, Existential risk, Autonomy, Moral responsibility, privacy, Unemployment*

Introduction

We have been using various machines since ancient times, and in the present time, the use of machines has increased significantly. Some people question whether the thinking of this machine has power or intelligence. Before Alan Turing maybe no one could prove that the machine has power or intelligence, this intelligence is not as sharp as natural intelligence. It is artificially imposed on the machine as seen in various games (go,). The intelligence of these machines has gradually developed to a great extent, with increasing human-likeness, which is called artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence is a branch of computer science. 'The term artificial intelligence (AI) was first used by John McCarthy in 1956'¹. He uses the term the summer conference at Dartmouth College.

Artificial intelligence has gradually grown and strengthened its base in various fields like engineering, mathematics, education, agriculture, health care, etc. Artificial intelligence can now do many things on its own without human help. They can learn on their own. They can correct their mistakes in the next case through deep learning and machine learning. Currently, AI is being used as a recommendation system in various companies, like Amazon, Facebook, Google, etc AI is being used as a voice recognition system by various companies, like Apple (Siri), Google (Google Assistant), Amazon (Alexa), etc, and now self-driving cars are the latest AI product in society. But what is AI? Generally, AI is a machine that can solve problem and act like human. Some definition of AI is given below—

- **Russell & Norvig define AI as** – 'AI as the study of agent that receive precepts from the environment and performs action'².
- **Kaplan and Haenlein (2019) define AI as** – 'a system's ability to correctly interpret external data, to learn from such data, and to use those learnings to achieve specific goals and tasks through flexible adaptation'³
- **Poole and Mackworth (2010) define AI as** – 'the fields that studies the synthesis and analysis of computational agents that act intelligence'⁴.

From my point of view, artificial intelligence is something that solves various essential problems and helps us achieve our goals, and it will be flexible, meaning

it will have the power to learn new things and adapt itself to new environments. That is, artificial intelligence is something that is supposed to make our daily tasks much easier.

There are two main types of artificial intelligence machines. They are weak AI (narrow intelligence) and strong AI (superintelligence). Weak AI has some specific functions. They can only specifically work specifically at a time. At present, we can see this type of AI machine. However, AI is constantly evolving. AI will improve a lot in the future and will be able to work on many things at the same time, this type of AI machine is called strong AI. 'Strong AI seeks to create an artificial person: a machine that has all the mental power we have, including phenomenal consciousness'⁵. That is, strong AI has the power to combine various tasks at a time.

Nowadays computer science is rapidly developing. Our universe has a technological revolution, one of which is Artificial Intelligence (AI). AI products or Agents have been rapidly used in our society in every field. Moreover, AI is used in the military, education, etc. in various humanitarian fields by which people are protected and educated. Moreover, AI agents are currently working as substitutes for various parts of the human body, so the issues of ethics come into the use of AI. Hence, some ethical questions arise regarding AI product use. We know that AI is helping our everyday lives in various fields. The rapid spread of AI technologies raises complex questions about their potential impact on humanity's future. Because we are not yet fully aware of the power of artificial intelligence.

The philosophical inquiry into existential risk engages with fundamental questions about meaning, value, and the nature of risk itself. This paper will critically analyse existential risks posed by AI, arguing for a proactive and ethically grounded response to the challenges that AI poses.

The nature of existential risk

Human Existential risks are often categorised into various domains, like natural disasters, nuclear warfare, pandemics, and technological risks. Now the rapid advancement of technology. Using this technology, technologists have created machines with human-like intelligence (AI). AI is currently being widely used in human society. While human society has benefited from the widespread use of AI in society, it has also faced some serious problems. One of the most important problems is the problem of human existence. Human society has adopted various methods to maintain its existence since ancient times. animal life has an intrinsic value and animals adapt to different environments to sustain this life. Preserving life falls within the laws of nature. But in the present era, due to the rapid development of technology, there is a crisis of human existence. According to philosophers like Nick Bostrom⁶, an existential risk could either annihilate intelligent life or permanently curtail humanity's potential. Given the rapid developments in AI, understanding the nature of these risks has become urgent⁷. Existential risk refers to events that could lead to human extinction or the permanent and drastic deterioration of human civilisation⁸. But how is human existence at risk in using Artificial intelligence? Philosophically, existential risks challenge our understanding of ethical responsibility, as well as our obligations to future generations. With the rapid advancements in AI, existential risks arise from unaligned objectives, superintelligence, and the potential misuse of powerful AI systems.

The use of artificial intelligence can risk human existence in three ways, they are—

1. We are putting ourselves at risk by using artificial intelligence extensively.
2. Humans are using artificial intelligence to risk the existence of another human being.
3. Artificial intelligence (AI) itself will create a risk to human existence.

1. We are putting ourselves at risk by using artificial intelligence extensively.

We have become overly dependent on AI. That's why our existence is at risk. There are various reasons for this, which are given below—

Addiction— The use of AI products has rapidly increased in today's society. With the use of AI, various tasks are being done very easily. Before the use of AI, humans used to do various tasks with their thinking and skills. At that time, experienced people were consulted before doing any complicated work; it is no longer necessary at present. As a result, the human brain is becoming lazy, losing creative skills in various subjects, and various diseases are occurring in the human body. Human existence can also be at risk due to addiction to various advanced games. Previously, if we wanted to do a calculation, we would do it in pen and copy or our minds. But nowadays, even for very small calculations, we use calculators. Currently using ChatGPT. By using this Chat GPT, we get information on various topics in an instant. As a result, laziness is being created among most people, and people's creative intelligence is being reduced.

2. Humans are using artificial intelligence to risk the existence of another human being.

A person or a group of people can endanger the existence of other people using this AI. It can happen in different ways. Which are given below.

Privacy— Privacy is very important in our human society, so different countries have made different types of laws regarding this privacy. The United States Supreme Court has often considered privacy as a function of context.⁹ AI systems collecting extensive data on individuals, institutions, government, or private companies raise concerns about data privacy and security.

'Consider, for example, privacy and data protection. AI, and in particular machine learning applications working with big data, often involves the collection and use of personal information. AI can also be used for surveillance, on the street, but also in the workplace and through smartphones and social media—everywhere. Often people do not even know that data is being gathered, or that the data they provided in one context is then used by third parties in another context. Big data also often means that data (sets) acquired by different organisations are being combined.'¹⁰

A person or group of people can use the confidential information of another person or group of people in various places and risk their existence. AI products are currently being used as human organ replacements, like space makers. AI products can also be hacked to endanger human existence, as shown in various movies.

Unemployment— The use of AI products has rapidly increased in today's society. AI products are being used in various sectors and replacing human labour. For example, various advanced products are being used in the agriculture field, like Seed sowing, pesticide application, crop harvesting, etc. AI products. AI products have been used in the medical field, like receptionist, nurses, diagnosis, and

surgery, etc. There are also many other fields like teaching, transportation, banking, etc. where human labour is being replaced by AI products. By this, a large part of the human society is admitted to unemployment. As a result, their livelihoods are going to be in crisis.

Identity and Consciousness— Another philosophical issue revolves around identity and consciousness in the age of AI. Can machines possess consciousness, and if so, what are the implications for human identity? The distinction between human and machine intelligence leads to ethical considerations about rights and moral status. If AI systems achieve a form of consciousness or sentience, it may necessitate a re-evaluation of human exceptionalism. As Thomas Nagel (1974) suggests, understanding another being's consciousness deeply influences how we relate to it.

3. Artificial intelligence itself will create a risk to human existence.

Artificial intelligence is currently being widely used in various sectors of our society. AI is continuously evolving. In the future, AI could even at risk to human existence, as shown in sci-fi movies. The reasons why they can put human existence at risk are given below.

Autonomy and Control— One central concern is the autonomy of AI systems. As AI becomes more capable of making decisions without human intervention, the boundaries of control and responsibility become blurred. Philosophically, this raises questions akin to those posed by the concept of free will. If an AI system makes a decision that leads to catastrophic outcomes, who bears responsibility? Should we view AI as an extension of human agency, or as a potential rival that challenges human authority and autonomy?

Superintelligence and Control Problem— One of the most discussed existential risks is the control problem associated with superintelligent AI. If an AI surpasses human intelligence, its goals and objectives could diverge significantly from human values, leading to potentially catastrophic outcomes. Bostrom (2014) emphasises the need to ensure that AI systems remain aligned with human intentions¹¹. This challenge raises profound metaphysical questions about the nature of intelligence and the unpredictability of advanced algorithms.

Resource Competition and Misuse— Humanity's historical tendency toward resource competition raises concerns that AI may exacerbate existing inequalities. The misuse of AI, for instance in autonomous weapons or surveillance, could lead to detrimental consequences for society. The creation of AI with the capability to manipulate information can threaten democratic processes, creating new avenues for conflict and instability. Such implications call for a rigorous examination of the socio-political dimensions of AI development.

Ethical Implications— The development and deployment of AI prompts ethical questions regarding the impact on society. Utilitarian perspectives may advocate for AI that maximises overall happiness, while deontological views stress the importance of moral duties and rights. Ensuring that AI aligns with human values requires robust ethical frameworks that encompass diverse perspectives. The challenge lies in integrating ethical considerations into AI system design and deployment, ensuring that humanity's existential concerns are prioritised.

Conclusion

The philosophical analysis of existential risks posed by artificial intelligence highlights the pressing need for a multidisciplinary approach to understanding and mitigating these threats. As AI technology advances, our ethical, moral, and exist-

tential boundaries will be continually tested. This necessitates a proactive stance in policy-making, emphasising alignment with human values and collective well-being. Engaging with philosophical discourse enables us to critically assess our relationship with AI and develop frameworks that prioritise humanity's survival and flourishing in an increasingly automated world.

Endnotes

1. <https://plato.stanford.edu/> p-1
2. Bartneck, Christoph, Lutge, Christoph, Wagner, Alan, and Welsh, Sean. An introduction to ethics in Robotics and AI. Springer, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-51110-4>. p-7.
3. Ibid, p-7
4. Ibid, p-7
5. <https://plato.stanford.edu/> p-30
6. He is a philosopher known from his work on existential risk, the anthropic principle, human enhancement ethics, whole brain emulation superintelligence risk and the reversal test.
7. Bostrom, N. Superintelligence: Paths, Dangers, Strategies. Oxford University Press.2014
8. Bostrom, N, Existential Risk Prevention as Global Priority. Global Policy, 2013, 4(1), 1-18.
9. Bartneck, Christoph, Lutge, Christoph, Wagner, Alan, and Welsh, Sean. An introduction to ethics in Robotics and AI. Springer, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-51110-4>. P-62
10. Coeckelbergh, Mark. AI Ethics. The MIT Press, Essential Knowledge Series, 2020, <https://lccn.loc.gov/2019018827>. p-98
11. Bostrom, N. Superintelligence: Paths, Dangers, Strategies. Oxford University Press.2014.

Bibliography

- Carsten Stahl, Bernd. “Artificial Intelligence for a Better Future”. Springer, Switzerland, 2021.
- Braun, Joachim Von. Srcher, Margaret S. Reichberg, Gregory M. Sorondo, Marceto Sanchez. “Robotics, AI, and Humanity”. Springer, Switzerland, 2021.
- Coeckelbergh, Mark. “AI ETHICS”. The MIT Press Essential Knowledge Series, 2020.
- Bartneck, Christoph. Lutge, Christoph. Wagner, Alan. Welsh, Sean. “An introduction to ethics in Robotics and AI”. Springer, Switzerland, 2021.
- Bostrom, N. “Superintelligence: Paths, Dangers, Strategies”. Oxford University Press.2014.
- Stahl, Bernd Carsten, “Artificial Intelligence for a Better Future An Ecosystem Perspective on the Ethics of AI and Emerging Digital Technologies”, Springer, Switzerland, 2020.
- Gross, Richard. “Psychology of The Science of Mind and Behaviour”. Hodder Education
- Hewstone Miles, D. Fincham, Frank & Foster, Jonathan,” Psychology”, BPS & Blackwell, UK, 2005.
- Haugeland, John, “Mind design II”, The MIT Press, England, 1997. (Edit. book)
- Crane, Tim, “Elements of Mind An Introduction to the Philosophy of Mind”, Oxford University Press, 2001.
- Searle, John. R. “Minds, brains, and programs”. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences* 3, 1980.